

EDUCATIONAL DIMENSIONS OF ENGLISH TEACHING WITHIN FUTURE TEACHER TRAINING PROGRAMS

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Abstract. The article examines the main tasks of methodological support for the educational process of training students - future teachers of English - to use game methods of control. Ways to improve curricula and programs within the framework of this area of training are proposed, and a teaching aid specially developed for the proposed special course is described.

Keywords: methodological support, game technologies, organization of control, special course.

INTRODUCTION

The qualifications of a modern teacher-philologist include requirements for both his theoretical and practical training. The theoretical training of a teacher-philologist involves the formation of knowledge about the main stages of development of language teaching methods and the basics of the theory of formation of communicative competence of students, knowledge of the characteristics of the subjects of training [1]. Practical training implies that a teacher-philologist has the ability to implement various functions: communicative, educational, developmental and educational. A foreign language teacher must also be able to carry out gnostic, constructive-planning, organizational functions, be able to organize all components of the educational process, including control, taking into account the characteristics of the subjects of training.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An analysis of the requirements for a modern foreign language teacher has shown that a graduate of this profile must be ready to solve, along with others, such

professional tasks as: using technologies that correspond to the age characteristics of students; implementing educational activities taking into account special educational needs, etc. In other words, specialists of this profile must, within the framework of general professional competencies, be able to carry out training and control taking into account the social, age, psychophysical and individual characteristics and needs of students [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the pedagogical conditions for the successful preparation of students — future teachers of English — for conducting game-based control of the learning outcomes of primary school students is scientifically based methodological support of the educational process [2]. In this case, methodological support means scientific, methodological, informational, and also psychological support for teaching students the game-based method of monitoring the foreign language communicative competence of primary school students. Based on the versatility of the concept of "methodological support", the following main tasks can be identified:

- introducing game-based control into curricula and programs of classes;
- developing methodological materials for teaching the organization of game-based forms of control;
- using new methods, forms, and means of teaching along with traditional ones;
- improving the pedagogical skills and methodological culture of teachers involved in preparing students for game-based control.

Let us consider these tasks in more detail. The first task is to include classes on game control in the curricula and programs. Since the programs generally allocate 4-6 hours for studying the essence of control at school (which, as practice shows, is clearly not enough), it is advisable to introduce a special course on “Organization of control of educational achievements of primary school students in a foreign language using game

technologies” as a supplement to the course on methods of teaching a foreign language at school. This special course is designed for 72 academic hours (2 EE), that is, for one semester. The special course should be held in the first semester for fourth-year students, since they have already completed the course on “Methods of Teaching a Foreign Language”, are familiar with the basics of pedagogy and psychology, and most importantly, they are preparing for teaching practice and obtaining a bachelor's degree. Contact classes should be allocated 34 hours (2 hours per week - 47% of the study time), the remaining hours should be devoted to independent preparation of students (53% of the study time). During independent preparation, students write reports on the studied sections, develop presentations, projects, prepare for participation in business role-playing games, round tables, seminars, and the final colloquium.

The topics of the special course classes were determined based on the results of the ascertaining experiment, during which the level of readiness of future teachers to apply game methods of control was determined. The majority of philology students showed an insufficient level of readiness for all criteria and indicators - 58.97%, 32.92% of students showed a satisfactory level of readiness, 3.84% - a reproductive level, and only 1.24% of students had a productive level of readiness.

Thus, the structure of the special course and the topics of the classes are aimed at obtaining by students the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the use of game control in English lessons in primary school.

The second task of methodological support is the development of methodological materials and teaching aids. For training within the framework of the special course, a teaching aid "Game organization of control of educational achievements of primary school students" was developed [3]. The manual contains theoretical information on monitoring the foreign language competence of primary school students (description of objects and functions of monitoring, list of requirements for monitoring), and shows the

age-related psychological and physical characteristics of primary school students as subjects of monitoring.

One of the new means of teaching students can be considered social networks, which have already entered the life of almost every person and are beginning to be increasingly used in the educational process [4]. With the help of information technology, teachers and students can not only reach a new level of communication, but also exchange experiences with colleagues from other Russian and foreign universities, participate in progressive projects in the educational sphere. Social networks provide an opportunity to intensify and modernize the learning process and control its results. Participation of students and teachers in social networks leads to the following positive changes in the educational process:

- students' motivation to master the educational material increases.
- when communicating with a teacher online, a student feels more free; a student and a teacher in a social network feel like equal partners, which positively affects the learning results [5].
- social networks provide more and more opportunities for interactive learning; holding a video conference, round table or brainstorming session online promotes a solid assimilation of educational material and the development of students' creative abilities.
- in a social network, it is convenient for a teacher to distribute assignments, check their completion, answer questions, and provide additional information [6].
- when using social networks for learning, a student can independently plan his or her study time, finding the optimal pace of work and simultaneously cultivating a sense of responsibility for its results.

CONCLUSION

In today's rapidly changing world, a teacher, including an English teacher, must be proactive, competent, responsible, and have a need for constant enrichment and

updating of knowledge and self-development. These qualities must be instilled in the process of training at a higher pedagogical educational institution, in particular, within the framework of independent work of students in performing creative educational and professional tasks. Thus, the implementation of the above-mentioned tasks of methodological support is a necessary condition for the successful training of future English teachers in the use of game-based control methods in elementary school lessons.

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